

Title: A Systematic Review of Fault Tolerance Techniques for Adaptive and Context-aware Systems

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Base keywords:

("adaptive system" OR "adaptive systems" OR "adaptive software" OR "autonomic" OR "context-aware" OR "context aware" OR "context-awareness" OR "context awareness" OR "self-adaptive" OR "self adaptive" OR "self-organising" OR "self organising" OR "self-organizing" OR "self organizing") AND ("fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR "fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable")

The base keywords were customized to each search engine as we show below:

Strings for ACM

(acmdlTitle:("adaptive system") OR acmdlTitle:("adaptive systems") OR acmdlTitle:("adaptive software") OR acmdlTitle:("autonomic") OR acmdlTitle:("context-aware") OR acmdlTitle:("context aware") OR acmdlTitle:("context-awareness") OR acmdlTitle:("context awareness") OR acmdlTitle:("self-adaptive") OR acmdlTitle:("self adaptive") OR acmdlTitle:("self-organising") OR acmdlTitle:("self organising") OR acmdlTitle:("self-organizing") OR acmdlTitle:("self organizing")) AND (acmdlTitle:("fault-tolerance") OR acmdlTitle:("fault tolerance") OR acmdlTitle:("fault-tolerant") OR acmdlTitle:("fault tolerant") OR acmdlTitle:("dependability") OR acmdlTitle:("dependable")))

OR

(recordAbstract:("adaptive system") OR recordAbstract:("adaptive systems") OR recordAbstract:("adaptive software") OR recordAbstract:("autonomic") OR recordAbstract:("context-aware") OR recordAbstract:("context aware") OR recordAbstract:("context-awareness") OR recordAbstract:("context awareness") OR recordAbstract:("self-adaptive") OR recordAbstract:("self adaptive") OR recordAbstract:("self-organising") OR recordAbstract:("self organising") OR recordAbstract:("self-organizing") OR recordAbstract:("self organizing")) AND (recordAbstract:("fault-tolerance") OR recordAbstract:("fault tolerance") OR recordAbstract:("fault-tolerant") OR recordAbstract:("fault tolerant") OR recordAbstract:("dependability") OR recordAbstract:("dependable")))

OR

(keywords.author.keyword:"adaptive system" OR keywords.author.keyword:"adaptive systems" OR keywords.author.keyword:"adaptive software" OR keywords.author.keyword:"autonomic" OR keywords.author.keyword:"context-aware" OR keywords.author.keyword:"context aware" OR keywords.author.keyword:"context-awareness" OR keywords.author.keyword:"context awareness" OR keywords.author.keyword:"self-adaptive" OR keywords.author.keyword:"self adaptive" OR keywords.author.keyword:"self-organising" OR keywords.author.keyword:"self organising" OR keywords.author.keyword:"self-organizing" OR keywords.author.keyword:"self organizing" AND (keywords.author.keyword:"fault-tolerance" OR keywords.author.keyword:"fault tolerance" OR keywords.author.keyword:"fault-tolerant" OR keywords.author.keyword:"fault tolerant" OR keywords.author.keyword:"dependability" OR keywords.author.keyword:"dependable"))

Strings for IEEE

("Document Title":"adaptive system" OR "Document Title":"adaptive systems" OR "Document Title":"adaptive software" OR "Document Title":"autonomic" OR "Document Title":"context-aware" OR "Document Title":"context aware" OR "Document Title":"context-awareness" OR "Document Title":"context awareness") AND ("Document Title":"fault-tolerance" OR "Document Title":"fault tolerance" OR "Document Title":"fault-tolerant" OR "Document Title":"fault tolerant" OR "Document Title":"dependability" OR "Document Title":"dependable")

("Document Title":"self-adaptive" OR "Document Title":"self adaptive" OR "Document Title":"self-organising" OR "Document Title":"self organising" OR "Document Title":"self-organizing" OR "Document Title":"self organizing") AND ("Document Title":"fault-tolerance" OR "Document Title":"fault tolerance" OR "Document Title":"fault-tolerant" OR "Document Title":"fault tolerant" OR "Document Title":"dependability" OR "Document Title":"dependable")

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"Abstract": "self organising" OR "Abstract": "self-organizing"
OR "Abstract": "self organizing")
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OR "Abstract": "dependable")

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OR "Author Keywords": "context-aware" OR "Author Keywords": "context aware" OR
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"Author Keywords": "fault tolerant" OR "Author Keywords": "dependability" OR "Author
Keywords": "dependable")

("Author Keywords": "self-adaptive" OR "Author Keywords": "self adaptive" OR "Author
Keywords": "self-organising"
OR "Author Keywords": "self organising" OR "Author Keywords": "self-organizing" OR
"Author Keywords": "self organizing")
AND ("Author Keywords": "fault-tolerance" OR "Author Keywords": "fault tolerance" OR
"Author Keywords": "fault-tolerant" OR
"Author Keywords": "fault tolerant" OR "Author Keywords": "dependability" OR "Author
Keywords": "dependable")

Strings for Science Direct

TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("adaptive system" OR "adaptive systems" OR "adaptive software" OR
"autonomic")
AND TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR
"fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable")

TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("context-aware" OR "context aware" OR "context-awareness" OR
"context awareness")
AND TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR
"fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable")

TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("self-adaptive" OR "self adaptive" OR "self-organising" OR "self
organising" OR "self-organizing" OR "self organizing")
AND TITLE-ABSTR-KEY("fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR
"fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable")

Strings for Scopus

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("adaptive system" OR "adaptive systems" OR "adaptive software" OR "autonomic")
AND ("fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR "fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable") AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "COMP") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENGI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("context-aware" OR "context aware" OR "context-awareness" OR "context awareness")
AND ("fault-tolerance" OR "fault tolerance" OR "fault-tolerant" OR "fault tolerant" OR "dependability" OR "dependable") AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "COMP") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENGI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("self-adaptive" OR "self adaptive" OR "self-organising" OR "self organising" OR "self-organizing" OR "self organizing")
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Strings for SpringerLink

(ti:"adaptive system" OR ti:"adaptive systems" OR ti:"adaptive software" OR ti:"autonomic" OR ti:"context-aware" OR ti:"context aware" OR ti:"context-awareness" OR ti:"context awareness" OR ti:"self-adaptive" OR ti:"self adaptive" OR ti:"self-organising" OR ti:"self organising" OR ti:"self-organizing" OR ti:"self organizing")
AND (ti:"fault-tolerance" OR ti:"fault tolerance" OR ti:"fault-tolerant" OR ti:"fault tolerant" OR ti:"dependability" OR ti:"dependable")

(ab:"adaptive system" OR ab:"adaptive systems" OR ab:"adaptive software" OR ab:"autonomic" OR ab:"context-aware" OR ab:"context aware" OR ab:"context-awareness" OR ab:"context awareness" OR ab:"self-adaptive" OR ab:"self adaptive" OR ab:"self-organising" OR ab:"self organising" OR ab:"self-organizing" OR ab:"self organizing")
AND (ab:"fault-tolerance" OR ab:"fault tolerance" OR ab:"fault-tolerant" OR ab:"fault tolerant" OR ab:"dependability" OR ab:"dependable")

within Computer Science and English
within Engineering English

Strings for Web of Science

Search by topic:

TS = ("adaptive system" OR "adaptive systems" OR "adaptive software" OR "autonomic" OR "context-aware" OR "context aware" OR "context-awareness" OR "context awareness" OR "self-adaptive" OR "self adaptive" OR "self-organising" OR "self organising" OR "self-organizing" OR "self organizing")

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Strings for Wiley

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